

VARIATION OF ABSOLUTE VISCOSITY WITH CONCENTRATION.
ORGANIC SOLUTES IN NON-AQUEOUS SOLVENTS

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The viscosity of non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents has been studied at different concentrations. It has been found that Taimini's second equation $\log \eta = \theta c + \phi$ is applicable to the most of the systems studied here. The values of the constants, θ and ϕ , of the above equation have been calculated.

In a previous communication by Bose (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 33) the variation of viscosity with concentration has been studied. In the present paper the same work has been extended to the other systems of organic solutes in non-aqueous solvents.

The experimental method employed for the determination of viscosity is the same as in the previous paper. Results obtained are given in Table I.

The viscosity was determined at four different concentrations and at various temperatures. The observations at only two different temperatures, lowest and the highest, are recorded below. The concentrations given are expressed in grams of anhydrous solute in 100 grams of pure solvent.

TABLE I

Solute.	Temp.	Viscosity at different concentrations.				
		Solvent = MeOH.				
		$c =$	68.0	74.0	83.0	93.0
Benzoic acid	30°		0.011960	0.012900	0.013600	—
	45°		0.009466	0.010020	0.010530	0.011330
Salicylic acid	35°	$c =$	65.0	72.0	75.0	88.0
	50°		0.010490	0.010860	0.011180	0.012620
Phthalic acid	35°		0.008273	0.008572	0.008818	0.009692
	50°	$c =$	24.6	29.5	33.0	37.0
Cinnamic acid	35°		0.009160	0.010010	0.01085	0.011680
	50°		0.007180	0.007900	0.008526	0.009060
<i>m</i> -Nitro benzoic acid	35°	$c =$	37.5	42.4	45.0	50.3
	50°		0.008921	0.009758	0.010140	0.010920
Succinic acid	35°		0.007246	0.007679	0.007970	0.008460
	50°	$c =$	110.7	144.40	156.6	167.0
Succinic acid	35°		0.018850	0.024850	0.027730	0.030250
	50°		0.014210	0.018030	0.020260	0.021620
Succinic acid	35°	$c =$	19.6	25.5	27.8	33.5
	50°		0.008055	0.009203	0.009556	—
			0.006460	0.007331	0.007603	0.008441

TABLE I (contd.)

Solute.	Temp.	Viscosity at different concentrations.			
		Solvent = Propyl alcohol.			
Benzoic acid	30°	$c = 40.0$	44.0	50.0	56.0
	45°	0.025310	0.026030	0.027240	0.028440
Salicylic acid	35°	$c = 35.4$	43.7	50.0	54.3
	50°	0.021300	0.022360	0.024270	0.024000
Phthalic acid	40°	$c = 5.6$	7.8	10.6	13.5
	55°	0.0163200	0.017320	0.018870	—
Cinnamic acid	35°	$c = 18.2$	24.4	30.3	34.2
	55°	0.020660	0.022240	0.024400	—
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	45°	$c = 78.4$	89.7	98.3	108.0
	55°	0.030070	0.032860	0.036200	0.039510
Succinic acid	40°	$c = 6.1$	7.5	8.8	9.8
	55°	0.016570	0.017200	0.017770	0.018880
Solvent = Butyl alcohol.					
Salicylic acid	35°	$c = 30.3$	39.0	44.5	50.5
	55°	0.024530	0.026560	0.027610	—
Phthalic acid	45°	$c = 4.9$	7.3	9.2	—
	50°	0.018060	0.019280	0.019850	—
Cinnamic acid	45°	$c = 15.7$	21.2	25.6	—
	55°	0.019320	0.020790	0.021800	—
Succinic acid	45°	$c = 2.7$	5.8	7.8	—
	55°	0.017040	0.018480	0.019430	—
Solvent = Acetone.					
Benzoic acid	33°	$c = 56.9$	53.0	62.5	69.1
	45°	0.006741	0.006647	0.007283	0.007500
Solvent = Nitrobenzene.					
Benzoic acid	40°	$c = 12.0$	16.0	21.0	—
	55°	0.016260	0.016750	0.017460	—
		0.013020	0.013330	0.013930	—

DISCUSSION

From the results given in Table I, the following types of curves have been plotted: (a) viscosity against concentration, (b) log viscosity against concentration. Of these two types of curves, log viscosity against concentration is found to be more applicable to these systems also. The results for the plot of log viscosity against concentration is given in Table II. The plotted curves have been divided into three categories, viz., (i) those which give a straight line, (ii) those giving a positive curvature and (iii) those which give negative curvature.

TABLE II

Straight line.		Positive curvature.	Negative curvature.
1.	MeOH—Succinic acid	1. PrOH—Succinic acid	1. Acetone—Benzoic acid
2.	„ — Benzoic acid	2. Nitrobenzene— Benzoic acid	
3.	„ — Salicylic acid		
4.	„ — Phthalic acid		
5.	„ — Cinnamic acid		
6.	„ — <i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid		
7.	PrOH — Benzoic acid		
8.	„ — Salicylic acid		
9.	„ — Phthalic acid		
10.	„ — Cinnamic acid		
11.	„ — <i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid		
12.	BuOH — Salicylic acid		
13.	„ — Cinnamic acid		

From the results given above it is observed that the second equation of Taimini

$$\log \eta = \theta c + \phi \dots \dots \dots (I)$$
 is obeyed by most of the systems studied here.

The values of θ and ϕ of the above equation (I) have been calculated for the systems studied here. The results for θ and ϕ are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Temp. = 45°.

Solute.	$\theta \times 10^{-3}$.	ϕ .	η of (calc.) η of pure solvent.	
			Solvent = MeOH.	
Benzoic acid	4.100	.6974	0.004982	0.004300
Salicylic acid	2.910	.7619	0.005780	
Phthalic acid	9.451	.6577	0.004546	
Cinnamic acid	5.146	.7022	0.005037	
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	3.428	.8198	0.006604	
Succinic acid	8.352	.6802	0.004790	

TABLE II—(contd.)

	$\theta \times 10^{-3}$.	ϕ .	η (calc.).	η of pure solvent.
Solvent=Pr.OH.				
Benzoic acid	2.770	.1371	0.013710	0.012600
Salicylic acid	3.227	.1105	0.012900	
Phthalic acid	11.900	.0979	0.012530	
Cinnamic acid	5.322	.1149	0.013030	
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	4.444	.1167	0.013090	
Succinic acid	10.370	.1076	0.012810	
Solvent=BuOH.				
Salicylic acid	3.300	.1905	0.015510	0.01590
Phthalic acid	11.940	.1975	0.015760	
Cinnamic acid	5.543	.1990	0.015850	
Succinic acid	28.500	.0650	0.011610	
Solvent=Acetone				
Benzoic acid	3.573	.5823	0.003820	
Solvent=Nitrobenzene				
Benzoic acid	3.250	.1379	0.013790	

From the results given in Table III the following observations may be made :

(1) For the solutions of propyl alcohol—phthalic acid, propyl alcohol—succinic acid and butyl alcohol—phthalic acid the difference between the values of viscosity calculated and the viscosity of the pure solvent is within 1%.

(2) For the solutions of propyl alcohol—salicylic acid, propyl alcohol—cinnamic acid, propyl alcohol—*m*-nitrobenzoic acid, butyl alcohol—salicylic acid and methyl alcohol—phthalic acid the difference is within 5%.

(3) For the solutions of methyl alcohol—succinic acid and propyl alcohol—benzoic acid the difference is within 5% to 10%.

(4) For the rest of the solutions studied in this paper the difference is above 10%.

It is observed that for the systems of propyl alcohol and butyl alcohol, the difference between the value of the viscosity calculated from Taimini's equation and the viscosity of the pure solvent is not much as compared to the systems of methyl alcohol. This may be due to the solvation being more marked in the systems of methyl alcohol than those in propyl alcohol and butyl alcohol.

The author wishes to express his sincere thanks to Dr. A. C. Chatterji for his valuable suggestions and guidance in this work and to the U.P. Government for the grant of a research fellowship.